

INDUSTRIALIZATION AND PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP FOR DEVELOPING DOMESTIC ECONOMIES IN THE THIRD WORLD COUNTRIES

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Abstract

The study is set to combat with and find ways of curbing the numerous challenges of industrialization and those of the public private partnership in the third world countries. There are a number of factors that pose serious challenge to these concepts. The problem of continuous control, subjugation and constant exploitation of the third world countries by the industrialized nations, have hindered the rapid growth and development of industrialization and public private partnership (PPP). Two theories were adopted in this study the Lewis Model of industrialization, presented in 1955 as well as the community development theory. Historical/Descriptive Survey design was adopted as methodology, and primary and secondary data were used for the analysis. The subsidiary objectives included finding out if the locally fabricated industrial machines can be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height. The three research questions to elicit answers from respondents included, 'can the locally fabricated industrial machines be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height? This was followed by the research hypotheses which were postulated in null. (H) forms to enable empirical verifications and statistical calculations in this study. The first among the hypotheses was that the locally fabricated industrial machines may likely be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height. Based on the findings, three recommendations were also put forward to resolve the issues found in the study. Among them was that, government should encourage the locally fabricated industrial machines to be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height in Nigeria.

Keywords: Industrialization, Public Private Partnership, Domestic Economies and Third World Countries.

1. Background to the study

The concepts of Industrialization and Public Private Partnership (PPA) have globally become very crucial in the development of contemporary societies in recent times. In the early 80s and late 90s, it was the practice that the local women made use of manual craters to crate cassava and pressed it with four long sticks held together at the base by a rope produced from the inner part of palm front, weaved together in the form of a ring and tight together on the top-side with two long ropes that were also produced from the inner part of palm front with each rope holding tight the two sticks together on the cassava paste that was already packed into a white sack bag. The cassava paste would be left in the tight condition over-night for it to drain away the water and starch.

On the following day, the women would lose the bag of cassava paste from the sticks and get it ready for sifting with a local sifter into a big basin. Thereafter, the sifted cassava (this time no more in the paste form but in a wet condition), awaits to be fried. The frying process was done with an open kind of frying pan prepared by the blacksmiths. It was usually very hot when suspended on the fire, burning with charcoal or firewood.

In my culture and tradition in parts of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, although men were not forbidden to fry garri, but the picture usually seems odd whenever a man sat at the fire place to fry it. People would wonder whether the man had no sisters or wife that should help him to fry the garri. As such, garri was most often fried by women in my locality. This process of making small quantity of garri for subsistence purposes usually took at least two days to be completed. By that estimation, one is left to wonder if just the subsistent quantity of garri produced basically for domestic use could take such amount of time, effort and, ingenuity, then the cost of producing garri in large quantity for commercial purposes at that time could be unimaginable. Yet, people were still involved in the commercial production of garri at that time using the same process.

In a similar process, the palm oil production was another very tasking and prolonged traditional agro-economic engagement before the advent of the locally fabricated machines for oil mill production. In this case, some men who learned how to climb the palm trees made use of raffia ropes extracted from palm wine trees for that purpose. The robes were specially weaved manually by specialists, and with cutlasses in their hands, the palm fruit tappers climbed the palm trees that yield ripe fruits and tapped the fruits. Thereafter, the women and young children (mostly from the kindred of the tapper), would pack the bunches of the palm fruits back home where they were usually kept for about a week or so for it to become softened and easy to prune and separate the seeds from the stalks and chaffs.

Often, the women (and sometimes, men) would separate the palm fruits from the chaffs and kept for processing. As early as 1.00 am or thereabouts, depending on the quantity of the palm fruits, the women would wake up and set their palm fruits on fire. After boiling the fruits for hours (in a large earthen pots) to ensure that by 3.00 am the palm fruits were properly cooked and were ready for pounding, the strong men will come out and do the pounding of the palm fruits with big wooden mortar and long wooden pestles. The mortars were carved out from big logs of wood and the pestles.

Before morning when others are waking up, it was always surprising that the process had gone very far. Most young people never met the pounding stage. But when they finally woke up, they will see their mothers and their assistants sorting and separating the chaffs from the kernel and draining the oil into basins. All the sorting process took place in large wooden canoe-like calabash. On the final analysis, it is important to note that what come out as the final products are: kernels, chaffs and oil. The oil is squeezed out of the chaffs into various sizes of calabashes or basins. However, the process was usually very tedious, and time and energy consuming. The younger people never liked this process, but they had no choice as most of their school fees, feeding money and clothing came from this process.

But, fortunately today, things have changed drastically. Various machines have been fabricated. While some of them are locally made in Nigeria, others are imported from the foreign countries to the country. For instance, a visit to a certain newly constructed Palm Oil Mill in Nya Odiong village in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area where the researcher comes from, exposed the researcher to this very Constituency Project which was attracted to Ikot Abasi Federal Constituency by the then House of Representatives member, Hon. Dr. Akpan Micah Umoh. In his remarks, Dr. Umoh assured the people that the plant saves time, man-power, cost, energy and also brings about higher productivity, output and efficiency as compared to the erstwhile traditional/manual method of palm oil production of our forebears".

The implication of what the Rep. said was that the functionality of the entire out-fit was that as soon as palm fruits were ferried from the bush, they were thrown into the machine (boiler) in bunches with the chaffs and the stalks without having to separate them. The boiler then boils the fruits at a certain temperature and when it is cooked, the machine pushes the chaffs out into a separator which further separates the chaffs from the real palm fruits and then throws chaffs out to one side and the palm fruits into the pounding machine. The pounder pounds the fruits and moves the whole lumps to another separator that distinctively separates the cannels from the fibers. The fibers get into the oil press and are pressed to extract oil from the fibers into big containers. And the process continues until the entire large quantity of palm fruits are processed. The process is time and energy saving. It is also very economical and can

continue as many times as possible in a day. That is what industrialization has brought to replace the crude methods of existence.

2. Statement of the Problem

The problem of industrialization in the third world countries is exactly as that related to technology. It cannot be transferred, rather, the developed countries hold sway to industrialization; as such, the problem of monopoly ensues. The industrialized nations feel more comfortable to continuously place the less developed or developing nations under their control in order to be able to continue to exploit both their ignorance as well as their bountiful natural resources. The researcher was bothered by the situation where the developing countries lack foreign technology, expertise, aids and capital to drive their industrialization process to the stage of also becoming an industrialized or developed nations.

For foreign technology, as stated earlier on, the developed nations can never transfer their technology to the developing nations (Udoh, 2014). In the developing nations, expertise is lacking because of the fear of impacting the requisite knowledge to the blacks by the white hegemons. They are seldom to train the blacks to know what the whites know and use to develop their countries. In a situation where a few blacks are trained and are exposed to this knowledge, such blacks are not allowed to return to their countries. They are made to sign citizenship with their countries and are given green cards (ibid.).

This also goes to buttress the point that the developed and industrialized nations do not want their technology to be transferred to the third world countries. The capitals of developing nations have become their capitals. The developed nations, over the years, strategically turned the capitals of the developing countries to become theirs through the sale of obsolete technology; through the sale of expertise and through other means of exploitation on the human and natural resources of these less developed nations. Having achieved that, the developed nations begin to offer some forms of assistance to the third world countries through foreign aids and loans, using powerful institutions as the World Bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF) to further siphon the resources of the blacks.

The idea of partnering with third world countries by the industrialized countries is not farfetched. It is the same strategy of exploiting the resources of the black nations, but taking a different form. Point of note is that the developed countries cannot embark on any venture that will not yield them profit. In order words, they pretend to help, yet they make so much profits out of the assistance that they render.

3. Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to investigate how industrialization and public private partnership (PPP) could be used for developing domestic economies in the third world countries.

The subsidiary objectives of the study include:

- i. To find out if the locally fabricated industrial machines can be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height.
- ii. To discover new ways to foster collaboration and innovation between industrialization and public private partnership.
- iii. To seek ways that can assist the third world countries to completely gain economic independence from the industrialized nations.

4. Research Questions

In order to elicit answers from respondents, the researcher asked the following questions:

- i. Can the locally fabricated industrial machines be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height?
- ii. What are the new ways to foster collaboration and innovation between industrialization and public private partnership?
- iii. Are there ways that can assist the third world countries to completely gain economic independence from the industrialized nations?

5. Research Hypotheses

In order to be able to carry out empirical verifications and statistical calculations in this study, three (3) hypotheses were formulated in null (H) forms. These are as stated below:

- i. The locally fabricated industrial machines may likely be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height.
- ii. There tend to be new ways to foster collaboration and innovation between industrialization and public private partnership.
- iii. There may perhaps, be ways that can assist the third world countries to completely gain economic independence from the industrialized nations.

6. Methodology of the Study

The methodology adopted in this research was the historical/descriptive survey design. Methods of enquiry included the primary and secondary methods of data collection. The primary method involved personal observation and interviews to people considered to be aware of and conversant with the problem at hand as well as the use of questionnaire forms. On the other hand, the secondary method of data collection included: text books, journals, conference papers, government's official publication newspapers, magazines and the internet.

7. **Significance of the study**

The significance of the study can be viewed in two perspectives, namely theoretical and empirical significance.

i. **Theoretical significance**

The research will contribute immensely to the existing body of knowledge, and as such, it will serve as reference materials for future researchers in the field of industrialization generally, and PPP, in particular.

ii. **Empirical significance**

The knowledge acquired from the study on industrialization and public private partnership will help to proffer lasting solution to the challenges surrounding the concept in Nigeria. It is hoped that the study will help the government, particularly the law makers to make suitable legislations that will encourage the continued collaboration between the two concepts industrialization and PPP. The experts will find this material useful in carrying out their official assignments, both in the public and private concerns. The executive also will realize the importance of preserving government equity share in the partnership business and as such, will put in place measures that will enhance the smooth operation and collaboration of industrialization and public private partnership.

8. **Definition of terms**

- i. **Industrialization:** The process in which a society or country (or world) transforms itself from a primarily agricultural society into one based on the manufacturing of goods and services. Industrialisation (in British English) or industrialization (in American English) is the period of social and economic change that transforms a human group from an agrarian society into an industrial one. It is a part of a wider modernization process, where social change and economic development are closely related with technological innovation, particularly with the development of large-scale energy and metallurgy production.
- ii. **Public Private Partnership (PPP):** Public Private Partnership (PPP) which can otherwise be abbreviated as P3 or P', as the name implies, "is a government service or private business venture which is funded and operated through a partnership of government and one or more private sector companies.
- iii. **Domestic Economies:** The concept of domestic economy refers to business activities or interactions that take place in a traditional or cultural domain, outside of foreign or international circle.
- iv. **Third World Countries:** This is a way of referring to poor or developing countries of Africa, Asia and Latin America, which is sometimes considered offensive, mostly by those referred to.

Review of Related Literature and Theoretical Framework

The concept of Industrialization

Udoh (2014) opines that industrialization (or industrialisation) is a process that happens in countries when they start to use machines to do work that was once done by people. Industrialization changes the society as it happens. During the industrialization of a country, people leave farming work to take higher paid jobs in factories in towns. Industrialization is part of a process where people adopt easier and cheaper ways to make things. Using better technology, it becomes possible to produce more goods in a shorter amount of time. A single person can produce more things.

After industrialization, people also do more specialized jobs. For example, before industrialization, a cobbler made the whole shoe. He worked on one pair of shoes, finished that, and then did the next pair of shoes. With industrialization, there are many people involved in making shoes. An individual shoemaker has a smaller task, however there is one person that cuts the sole of the shoe, another person stitches it on. In short there is division of labour. The machines to make the shoes cost a lot of money so the factory will be owned by a rich person who can afford the machines

The process in which a society or country (or world) transforms itself from a primarily agricultural society into one based on the manufacturing of goods and services. Individual manual labor is often replaced by mechanized mass production and craftsmen are replaced by assembly lines. Characteristics of industrialization include the use of technological innovation to solve problems as opposed to superstition or dependency upon conditions outside human control such as the weather, as well as more efficient division of labor and economic growth.

Industrialisation (in British English) or industrialization (in American English) is the period of social and economic change that transforms a human group from an agrarian society into an industrial one. It is a part of a wider modernization process, where social change and economic development are closely related with technological innovation, particularly with the development of large-scale energy and metallurgy production. It is the extensive organization of an economy for the purpose of manufacturing. Industrialization also introduces a form of philosophical change where people obtain a different attitude towards their perception of nature, and a sociological process of ubiquitous rationalization.

There is considerable literature on the factors facilitating industrial modernization and enterprise development. Key positive factors identified by researchers have ranged from favourable politico-legal environments for industry and commerce, through abundant natural resources of various kinds, to plentiful supplies of

relatively low-cost, skilled and adaptable labour. As industrial workers' incomes rise, markets for consumer goods and services of all kinds tend to expand and provide a further stimulus to industrial investment and economic growth. The first country to industrialize was the United Kingdom during the Industrial Revolution in the 18th century. By the end of the 20th century, East Asia had become one of the most recently industrialized regions of the world.

Historical perspective of industrialization

Most pre-industrial economies had standards of living not much above subsistence, among that the majority of the population were focused on producing their means of survival. For example, in medieval Europe, as much as 80% of the labour force was employed in subsistence agriculture. Some pre-industrial economies such as classical Athens had trade and commerce as significant factors and so native Greeks could enjoy wealth far beyond a sustenance standard of living through the use of slavery.

Famines were frequent in most pre-industrial societies, although some such as the Netherlands and England of the 17th and 18th centuries, the Italian city states of the 15th century, the medieval Islamic Caliphate, and the ancient Greek and Roman civilizations were able to escape the famine cycle through increasing trade and commercialization of the agricultural sector. It is estimated that during the 17th century, Netherlands imported nearly 70% of its grain supply and in the 5th century BC, Athens imported three-quarters of its total food supply. Industrialization through innovation in manufacturing processes first started with the Industrial Revolution in the north-west and Midlands of England in the 18th century. It spread to Europe and North America in the 19th century.

Industrialization and the Third World Countries

It would be noted that despite the goodness of industrialization which includes time saving, maximization of profit, large scale production of goods and services, innovation, specialization, division of labour, etc., industrialization down-sizes the labour strength in any organization or society (Udoh, 2014).

Take for instance, in a trip for a survey in a local shoe-making factory that had four staff to handle shoe mending daily now purchased both mending and shoe filing machines. It was found that the time that each of the four staff spent in mending one shoe could be used by the business owner alone to produce four shoes a day with the help of the machines. This development made the proprietor of the shoe mending factory to sack the three others and save money from their monthly stipends, while only one staff was retained to operate the two machines at the same salary rate. He rather advertised for trainees to apply in the shoe making company. The trainees were

not on monthly salaries from the company, yet they increase the productivity level of the company free of charge. Incidentally, industrialization takes the place of labour force and renders people jobless. This joblessness also renders an average Nigerian household or family hungry and famished.

Also taking into consideration the just concluded Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) examination. Before now, everything about JAMB was done manually by humans. But in recent times, the introduction of computer-based examination (e-examination) renders a whole spectrum of Nigerians who used to serve as supervisors, centre coordinators, examiners, etc. jobless. This is because electronic devices have taken over these manual duties that used to create employment opportunities for Nigerians. In recent times, many employees have lost their jobs due to the introduction of technology like computers, laptops, telephones, internet, etc. Lately, letter writing is no longer in vogue. Mails and parcels are rarely being conveyed lately to the owners by mail boys who were employees of post offices or courier companies. Most of the works that were done by mail boys and expert riders are now taken over by the internet.

Industrialization in Africa: can the continent make it?

Mbae, L. (2006) cited in Udoh (2014) propped whether the continent of Africa will be able to make industrialization to happen as it is happening in developed countries. According to him, without strong industries to create jobs and add value to raw materials, African countries risk remaining shackled by joblessness and poverty. Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana produce 53 percent of the world's cocoa. But the supermarket shelves in Abidjan and Accra, their respective capitals, are stacked with chocolates imported from Switzerland and the UK, countries that do not farm cocoa. This scenario is repeated throughout the continent in different contexts.

For example, Nigeria, the world's sixth-largest producer of crude oil, exports more than 80% of its oil but cannot refine enough for local consumption. In 2013, it spent about \$6 billion subsidizing fuel imports. In such apparently baffling scenarios lies one of Africa's greatest challenges and opportunities. The continent possesses 12 percent of the world's oil reserves, 40 percent of its gold and between 80 percent and 90 percent of its chromium and platinum, according to a 2013 report from the UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). It is also home to 60 percent of the world's underutilized arable land and has vast timber resources. Yet together, African countries account for just 1 percent of global manufacturing, according to the report.

rose from \$1,920 to \$6,496 between 1976 and 2012, according to the World Bank. While much responsibility lies with African governments, the continent's private sectors must play their part in improving co-ordination between farmers, growers, processors and exporters to increase competitiveness in the value chain and ensure the price, quality and standards that world markets demand.

Tony Elumelu, chairman of Nigerian-based investment company, Heirs Holdings, and Carlos Lopes, the executive secretary of the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, advocate what they call "Afri-capitalism", a private sector-led partnership focused on the continent's development. "Private-sector business leaders must also do more to tackle poverty and drive social progress by ensuring that long-term value addition as well as short-term gain is built into their business model," they wrote in a joint article for CNN in November 2013. Next, African countries must pursue beneficial economic strategies with their neighbours. Regional integration would help reduce the regulatory burden facing African industries by harmonizing policies and restraining unfavourable domestic programmes. It would boost inter and intra-African trade and accelerate industrialization. The right recipe for regional integration requires countries to concentrate on commodities in which they have a competitive advantage. For example, Benin and Egypt could concentrate on cotton, Togo on cocoa, Zambia on sugar-each country trading in bigger regional markets.

Agriculture, which employs over 65 percent of the continent's population, according to the World Bank, could become a springboard towards industrialization. It can provide raw materials for other industries, as well as promote what economists call backward integration, in which a company connects with a supplier further back in the process, such as a food manufacturer merging with a farm. This is already under way in Nigeria. The diversified BUA Group "will process 10m tons of cane to produce 1m tons of refined sugar annually", according to Chimaobi Madukwe, the company's chief operating officer. Sustained investment and improvements in infrastructure are also needed throughout the continent. Countries everywhere, not just in Africa, cannot establish competitive industrial sectors and promote stronger trade ties if saddled with substandard, damaged or non-existent infrastructure.

"Developing industries require sustained electricity supply, smooth transportation, and other very basic infrastructure facilities, which at present, are still not enough to ensure operations," said Xue Xiaoming, vice-chairman of the Nigerian Chinese Chamber of Commerce and Industry. Africa's poor roads, railways and other transport networks, faulty communications, and unreliable and insufficient energy result in high production and transaction costs. "It takes 28 days to move a 40-foot container from the port of Shanghai, China to Mombasa, Kenya at a cost of \$600,

while it takes 40 days for the same container to reach Bujumbura, Burundi, from Mombasa at a cost of \$8,000," explained Rosemary Mburu, a consultant at the Institute of Trade Development in Nairobi. "This represents double the time at 13 times the cost," she added.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) should be developed to stimulate massive investments in infrastructure, which could have a multiplier effect on economic growth. Finally, without education, the continent cannot succeed in its drive towards industrialization. PPPs should be pursued in this area too, because governments often lack the skills and finances to carry out technical training. Private sector companies would benefit from a skilled and competent workforce.

The country would benefit from a stronger economy blessed with less unemployment and higher incomes.

- Historically, countries have succeeded by focusing on education in science and technology and promoting research. For example, in the 1960s and 1970s South Korea -like Singapore, Taiwan and Hong Kong-reformed its education system and made elementary and high school compulsory.
- From an adult literacy rate of less than 30 percent in the late 1930s, South Korea now boasts a literacy rate of nearly 100% and has one of the highest levels of education anywhere in the world, according to UNESCO, the UN's education agency. Its highly skilled population has helped South Korea to become one of the world's foremost exporters of high-tech goods.

Africa, the world's youngest continent, is currently undergoing a powerful demographic transition. Its working-age population, which is currently 54 percent of the continent's total, will climb to 62 percent by 2050. In contrast, Europe's 15-64-year-olds will shrink from 63 percent in 2010 to 58 percent. During this time, Africa's labour force will surpass China's and will potentially play a huge role in global consumption and production. Unlike other regions, Africa will neither face a shortage in domestic labour nor worry about the economic burden of an increasingly ageing population for most of the 21 st century.

This "demographic dividend" can be cashed in to stimulate industrial production. An influx of new workers from rural areas into the cities, if harnessed correctly and complemented with the appropriate educational and institutional structures and reforms, could lead to a major productivity boom. This would then increase savings and investment rates, spike per capita GDP, and prompt skills transfers. Reduced dependency levels would then free up resources for economic development and investment.

Without effective policies, however, African countries risk high youth unemployment, which may spark rising crime rates, riots and political instability. Rather than stimulating a virtuous cycle of growth, the continent could remain trapped in a vicious circle of violence and poverty. The continent's youth represent a huge potential comparative advantage and a chance to enjoy sustained catch-up growth. Or they could remain shackled in joblessness and become a major liability. Africa is ripe for industrialization. A strong and positive growth trajectory, rapid urbanization, stable and improving economic and political environments have opened a window of opportunity for Africa to achieve economic transformation.

Public Private Partnership (PPP)

On the other hand, the concept of Public Private Partnership (PPP) which can otherwise be abbreviated as P3 or P³ as the name implies "is a government service or private business venture which is funded and operated through a partnership of government and one or more private sector companies. The main idea here is that partnership is the coming together, or the co-operation between one party and the government. The assessment of the subsistent operations of the production of both garri and palm produce in a traditional locality above, can help to draw a safe conclusion that the local producers have the technical know-how, resilience and energy to embark on such a tedious task, but they have less capital and machines or technology to drive their business to a commercial level of production.

This is the thought that bothered the mind of the researcher to suggest to government to partner not just with the local agro-farmers but with the entire agro-business outfit for higher productivity. It is, however, on record that Malaysia imported her first oil palm seedlings from Nigeria that was the leading oil palm producer in the world in the 70s. But today, Malaysia is one of the foremost countries in the world with the highest level of production of palm produce. It would be recalled that before the oil boom in Nigeria, agriculture was the main stay of Nigeria's economy. As soon as oil was discovered, agriculture diminished almost and disappearing. Nigeria's economy now draws its strength from the proceeds of oil.

The point here is that, Nigeria as a country having invested in oil, oil in return, is sustaining the Nigeria's economy. If Nigeria also invests part of its huge resources in partnering the local producers of cassava and palm oil produce in parts of the country, this sector of the economy can also sustain, to a large extent, the country's economy. Udoh, et al (2005:291) assert that, "Palm produce contributes more than 15% of the non-oil revenue of Nigeria. The industry provides extensive employment opportunities for Nigerians involved in the production, processing, marketing and distribution of both the main raw materials and the downstream products above.

According to the authors, "before 1960, Nigeria was the world's leading producer and exporter of palm produce. Since then, however, she lost that position to other countries. Malaysia alone, for instance, accounted for about 60.3% of the world palm oil production in 1986, while Indonesia and Nigeria produced 17.5% and 4.5% respectively. In 1989, the total production figure for the world and Africa were 10.17 and 1.56 million tons respectively. Malaysia still maintained the lead with a production rate of 6.1 million tones".

Public Private Partnership (PPP) is a concept that is newly and globally accepted, adopted and practiced in many countries of the world. As the name implies, Public-Private Partnership (PPP) is a contemporary public administration as well as development administration concept that has helped in the rapid development of many countries of the world when adopted. After considering the origin of the concept, effort will be made to run through some developed countries like Britain, Australia, Canada, India, Japan, Philippines, Puerto Rico and Russia, with emphasis on its impact on the development of the third world economies. Both the growth and the decline of the concept will be considered before looking at the various controversies that surrounds the concept.

Having said that, the work of Udoh, (2014) will serve a great deal in attempting to galvanize the local economies to embrace industrialization through Public Private Partnership (PPP) for the purpose of over-hauling domestic economies of the world.

A Public-Private Partnership (PPP) is a government service or private business venture which is funded and operated through a partnership of government and one or more private sector companies. These schemes are sometimes referred to as PPP, P3 or P³. PPP involves a contract between a public sector authority and a private party, in which the private party provides a public service or project and assumes substantial financial, technical and operational risk in the project. In some types of PPP, the cost of using the service is borne exclusively by the users of the service and not by the taxpayer. In other types (notably the private financial initiative), capital investment is made by the private sector on the basis of a contract with government to provide agreed services and the cost of providing the service is borne wholly or in part by the government.

Government contributions to a PPP may also be in kind (notably the transfer of existing assets). In projects that are aimed at creating public goods like in the infrastructure sector, the government may provide a capital subsidy in the form of a one-time grant, so as to make it more attractive to the private investors. In some other cases, the government may support the project by providing revenue subsidies,

including tax breaks or by removing guaranteed annual revenues for a fixed time period. There are usually two fundamental drivers for PPPs. Firstly, PPPs are claimed to enable the public sector to harness the expertise and efficiencies that the private sector can bring to the delivery of certain facilities and services traditionally procured and delivered by the public sector.

Secondly, a PPP is structured so that the public sector body seeking to make a capital investment does not incur any borrowing. Rather, the PPP borrowing is incurred by the private sector vehicle implementing the project and therefore, from the public sector's perspective, a PPP is an "off-balance sheet" method of financing the delivery of new or refurbished public sector assets.

Typically, a private sector consortium forms a special company called a "special purpose vehicle" (SPV) to develop, build, maintain and operate the asset for the contracted period. In cases where the government has invested in the project, it is typically (but not always) allotted an equity share in the SPV.] The consortium is usually made up of a building contractor, a maintenance company and bank lender(s). It is the SPV that signs the contract with the government and with subcontractors to build the facility and then maintain it. In the infrastructure sector, complex arrangements and contracts that guarantee and secure the cash flows make PPP projects prime candidates for project financing. A typical PPP example would be a hospital building financed and constructed by a private developer and then leased to the hospital authority.

The private developer then acts as a landlord, providing housekeeping and other non-medical services while the hospital itself provides medical services. A 2013 study published in State and Local Government Review found that definitions of public-private partnerships vary widely between municipalities: "Many public and private officials tout public-private partnerships for any number of activities, when in truth the relationship is contractual, a franchise, or the load shedding of some previously public service to a private or nonprofit entity." A more general term for such agreements is "shared service delivery" municipalities joining together, with private firms, or with non-profits to provide services to citizens.

Origin of Public Private Partnership PPP

Pressure to change the standard model of public procurement arose initially from concerns about the level of public debt, which grew rapidly during the macroeconomic dislocation of the 1970s and 1980s. Governments sought to encourage private investment in infrastructure, initially on the basis of accounting fallacies arising from the fact that public accounts did not distinguish between recurrent and capital expenditures. The idea that private provision of infrastructure

represented a way of providing infrastructure at no cost to the public has now been generally abandoned; however, interest in alternatives to the standard model of public procurement persisted. In particular, it has been argued that models involving an enhanced role for the private sector, with a single private-sector organization taking responsibility for most aspects of service provisions for a given project, could yield an improved allocation of risk, while maintaining public accountability for essential aspects of service provision.

Initially, most public-private partnerships were negotiated individually, as one-off deals, and much of this activity began in the early 1990s. PPPs are organized along a continuum between public and private nodes and needs as they integrate normative, albeit separate and distinct, functions of society the market and the commons. A common challenge for PPPs is allowing for these fluctuations and reinforcing the intended partnership without diminishing either sector. Multi-sectoral or collaborative, partnering is experienced on a continuum of private to public in varying degrees of implementation according to the need, time restraints, and the issue at hand. Even though these partnerships are now common, it is normal for both private and public sectors to be critical of the other's approach and methods. It is at the merger of these sectors that we see how a unified partnership has immediate impact in the development of communities and the provision of public services. PPP in Specific Countries: How it worked for them

* **Britain**

In 1992, the Conservative government of John Major in the UK introduced the private finance initiative (PFI), the first systematic programme aimed at encouraging public-private partnerships. The 1992 programme focused on reducing the Public Sector Borrowing Requirement, although, as already noted, the effect on public accounts was largely illusory. The Labour government of Tony Blair, elected in 1997, expanded the PFI initiative but sought to shift the emphasis to the achievement of "value for money," mainly through an appropriate allocation of risk. However, it has since been found that many programs ran dramatically over budget and have not presented as value for money for the taxpayer with some projects costing more to cancel than to complete.

* **Australia**

A number of Australian state governments have adopted systematic programmes based on the PFI. The first, and the model for most others, is Partnerships Victoria.

* **Canada**

The federal conservative government under Stephen Harper in Canada solidified its commitment to P3s with the creation of a crown corporation, P3 Canada Inc in

2009. The Canadian vanguards for P3s have been provincial organizations, supported by the Canadian Council for Public-Private Partnerships established in 1993 (a member-sponsored organization with representatives from both the public and the private sectors). As a proponent of the concept of P3s, the Council conducts research, publishes findings, facilitates forums for discussion and sponsors an Annual Conference on relevant topics, both domestic and international. Each year the Council celebrates successful public-private partnerships through the National Awards Program held concurrently with the annual conference in November. At lower levels of government P3s have been used to build major infrastructure projects like transit systems, such as Viva (bus rapid transit) and Ontario Highway 407.

* **India**

The Government of India defines a P3 as "a partnership between a public sector entity (sponsoring authority) and a private sector entity (a legal entity in which 51% or more of equity is with the private partner/s) for the creation and/or management of infrastructure for public purpose for a specified period of time (concession period) on commercial terms and in which the private partner has been procured through a transparent and open procurement system."

The union government has estimated an investment of \$320 billion in the infrastructure in the 10th plan. The major infrastructure development projects in the Indian state of Maharashtra (more than 50%) are based on the P3 model. In the 2000s, other states such Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Tamil Nadu also adopted this model. Sector-wise, the road projects account for about 53.4% of the total projects in numbers, and 46% in terms of value. Ports come in the second place and account for 8% of the total projects (21% of the total value). Other sectors including power, irrigation, telecommunication, water supply, and airports have gained momentum. through the P3 model. As of 2011, these sectors are expected get an investment of Rs. 20,27,169 crore (according to 2006-2007 WPI).

* **Japan**

In Japan since the 1980s, the third sector refers to joint corporations invested both by the public sector and private sector. In rail transport terms, a third sector railway line is a short line or network of lines operated by a small operator jointly owned by a prefectural/municipal government and smaller interests. Third sector lines are generally former JR Group (or Japanese National Railways (JNR) before 1987) lines that were divested from the national company.

* **Philippines**

The Philippine Government maintains an online list of PPP projects. Wikipedia articles on specific PPP projects in the Philippines are categorized into Categories: Proposed infrastructure in the Philippines.

* **Puerto Rico**

Wikipedia articles on specific PPP projects in Puerto Rico are categorized into Categories: Public-private partnerships in Puerto Rico.

* **Russia**

The first attempt to introduce PPP in Russia was made in St. Petersburg (Law #627-100 (25.12.2006), "On St. Petersburg participation in public-private partnership"). Nowadays, there are special laws about PPP in 69 subjects of Russian Federation. But the biggest part of them are just declarations. Besides PPP in Russia is also regulated by Federal Law #115-FZ (21.07.2005) "On concessional agreements" and Federal Law #94-FZ (21.07.2005) "On Procurement of Goods, Works and Services for State and Municipal Needs". In some ways PPP is also regulated by Federal Law №116-FZ (22.07.2005).

"On special economic zones" (in terms of providing business benefits on special territories in the broadest sense it is a variation of PPP), still all those laws and documents do not cover all possible PPP forms. In February, 2013 experts rated Subjects of Russian Federation according to their preparedness for implementing projects via public-private partnership. The most developed region is Saint Petersburg (with rating 7.8), the least - Chukotka (rating 0.0). By 2013 there are near 300 public-private partnership projects in Russia.

7. **Theoretical Framework**

Two theories adopted in this study are Structural Change Theory - The Lewis Model for industrialization, and the PPP Management Contract theory found to be the most appropriate for the study.

1. **Structural Change Theory - The Lewis Model**

The Lewis model presented in 1955, dominated development theory between the 1960s and 1970s. It is also known as the two-sector model, and the surplus labor model. It focused on the need for countries to transform their structures away from agriculture, with low productivity of labor; towards industrial activity, with a high productivity of labor.

In the Lewis model, the line of argument runs:

- i. An economy starts with two sectors: a rural agricultural sector and an urban industrial sector. Agriculture generally under-employs workers and the marginal productivity of agricultural labor is virtually zero.
- ii. Therefore, transferring workers out of agriculture does not reduce productivity in the whole economy.
- iii. Labor is then released for work in the more productive, urban, industrial sector.

- iv. Industrialization is now possible, given the increase in the supply of workers who have moved from the land.
- v. Industrial firms start to make profits, which can be re-invested into even more industrialization, and capital starts to accumulate.
- vi. As soon as capital accumulates, further economic development can sustain itself.

2. **Public private partnership approaches** can be categorized into four modes, namely:

- i. Management Contracts
- ii. Provision of infrastructure facilities through small scale private suppliers.
- iii. User Fee Public Private Partnership
- iv. Public private partnership based on readymade service (availability-based

But, for reasons of appropriateness, the first approach will be adopted in this study.

Management Contracts

Entering into an agreement by a government with the private sector relating to supply of certain service either on short-term or long-term basis on a limited term is described as Management Contracts. Mostly, the private sector participation is obtained through this method to get the services like rural roads, drinking water supply, and sanitation, etc. Under this method, the government institutions undertake their responsibility in providing the relevant service by continuously investing in the same and the private sector gets involved by way of a short-term or long-term contractual agreements only for the implementation of providing and maintaining such services.

Specific Case Studies/Conclusion

In specific terms, it would be safe to conclude that while some PPP projects have proceeded smoothly, others have been highly controversial. Australian examples include the Airport Link, the Cross City Tunnel, and the Sydney Harbour Tunnel, all in Sydney; the Southern Cross Station redevelopment in Melbourne; and the Robina hospital in Queensland.

In India, public-private partnerships have been extremely successful in developing infrastructure, particularly road assets under the National Highways Authority of India and Midday Meal Scheme with Akshaya Patra Foundation.

In Canada, public-private partnerships have become significant in both social and infrastructure development. PPP Canada Inc. was created as a Crown corporation

with an independent Board of Directors reporting through the Minister of Finance to Parliament. Its mandate is to improve the delivery of public infrastructure by achieving better value, timeliness and accountability to taxpayers, through P3s.

The Corporation became operational in February 2009 with the appointments of a chair of the board of directors and a chief executive officer. PPPs exist in a variety of forms in British Columbia through the focused efforts of Partnerships BC, a company registered under the Business Corporations Act that is wholly owned by the Province of British Columbia and reports to its shareholder, the Minister of Finance. Projects include the Canada Line rapid transit line, the Abbotsford Hospital and Cancer Centre and the Sea-to-Sky Highway project. In Quebec, a number of notable PPPs include the McGill University Health Centre, the new western extension of Auto-route 30 and Université de Montreal's Hospital Research Center.

In the UK, two-thirds of the London Underground PPP was taken back into public control in July 2007 after only four and a half years at an estimated cost of £2 billion and the remaining one-third was taken back into public control in May 2010 after seven and a half years for a purchase price of £310m. The Government had paid advisers £180m for structuring, negotiating and implementing the PPP and had reimbursed £275m of bid costs to the winning bidders. The 30-year PPP contract for the refurbishment of the MOD Main Building in London was estimated to give a saving of only £100,000 as compared to the £746.2m cost of public procurement. The refinancing of the Fazakerley Prison PFI contract following the completion of construction delivered an 81% gain to the private sector operator.

The NATS PPP saw 51% of the UK's air traffic control service transferred to the private sector. However, following the decline in air traffic after the September 11 attacks, the Government and BAA Limited each invested £65m in the private sector operator in 2003. In Newfoundland, Robert Gillespie Reid contracted to operate the railways for fifty years from 1898, though originally, they were to become his property at the end of the period (Udoh, 2014).

Recommendations

Based on the narrative historical facts embedded in this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. That government should encourage the locally fabricated industrial machines to be improved upon to drive the third world industries to an enviable height in Nigeria.
- ii. As part of discovering new ways to foster collaboration and innovation between industrialization and public private partnership, more people's groups should form themselves into partnership with existing private concerns

around their environments in order encourage PPP and also stimulate industrialization in such communities.

- iii. Finally, both government and the private sector should seek ways that can assist the third world countries to completely gain economic independence from the industrialized nations.

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